

Chemical analysis of limestone and dolomite using capillary electrophoresis

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Abstract : A new analytical protocol has been developed for chemical analysis of limestone and dolomite using capillary electrophoresis (CE). CE is a hybrid technique of chromatography and electrophoresis and hence separates individual type of ions and quantifies them. In this method, Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions were separated from other ions inside the capillary and quantified individually. The developed analytical protocol is cheaper, faster and accurate compared to the existing analytical methods using ICP-OES and AAS as it does not require any gases during analysis and avoids all types of interferences. The linearity, repeatability and reproducibility of the method were excellent with relative standard deviation below 2%. The analysis method has been validated using Certified Reference Materials.

Keywords : Capillary electrophoresis, dolomite, limestone, chemical analysis.

Introduction

Limestone and dolomite are an important class of industrial raw materials used in many industries including steel, cement, and paint industry. The amount of Ca and Mg present in these raw materials determines its industrial usefulness and hence its commercial value. Chemical analysis of limestone and dolomite to determine the Ca and Mg content is generally done by conventional analysis (gravimetric and titrimetric), ion chromatography, or by using spectroscopic instruments like Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) and Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectrophotometer (ICP-OES). The conventional analysis is a tedious, time consuming and error prone method as it depends a lot on the analytical skill of the analyst. On the other hand, Ca and Mg analysis using AAS and ICP-OES is associated with severe matrix and spectral interferences and specific masking agents (e.g. lanthanum chloride) need to be added carefully to the solution mixture to get accurate results. Slight variation in the quantity of the added masking agent often leads to very inaccurate results. Ion chromatography (IC) is an efficient technique for Ca and Mg ion analysis in neutral or near neutral solution. However, it is often very difficult to analyze Ca and Mg strongly acidic samples. Limestone and dolomite has to be dissolved in strong acidic solutions before analysis using IC.

Therefore, an alternate efficient method for chemical analysis of dolomite and limestone is strongly needed which is cheaper, faster, and free from interferences.

Capillary electrophoresis (CE) is a hybrid technique of electrophoresis and chromatography which involves separation of the ions inside the capillary using voltage and quantification of each ion individually. Therefore, it is free from matrix interference and spectral interference and is a very efficient technique for analysis of ions. CE is routinely used for analysis of complex biological samples like DNA, proteins, urine, analysis of chiral drug molecules and also for analysis of environmental samples like water, fruit juice, wine, etc.¹⁻⁵. Now-a-days, CE becomes acknowledged as a powerful method for inorganic-ion separations and in many instances the method is shown superior to the conventional ion chromatography technique for ionic multispecies analysis. The advantages of CE over IC include high separation efficiency, low material and sample consumption, and relatively short analysis times⁶. Another major practical advantage of CE over IC is a greater tolerance to complex matrices which can be processed without extensive pre-treatment.

There are a few reports of analysis of Ca and Mg using CE in water and beverage samples in which the concentration of these ions are in 1–50 ppm level and the solution is of neutral pH⁷⁻¹⁰. CE has also been success-

fully used for the analysis of a wide range of industrial samples and technical materials^{1,11}. For example, Siren *et al.* developed a process control system for on-line monitoring of anion and cation levels in the process waters of pulp and paper industry¹¹. Also, reliable CE procedures were developed for measuring ionic contaminants in semiconductor clean room wipers, anionic impurities in electrodeposition coatings, the contents of anions in Bayer liquid, sludge and thermal power plant process samples, spent fixing solutions, the simultaneous determination of common anions and cations in cosmetics, and for screening inorganic cation impurities in drug substance samples¹. However, there is no report of analysis of Ca and Mg in highly acidic mediums and also for samples in which Ca and Mg content is very high (30–40% as in limestone and dolomite). In fact, there is no report of analysis of any metallurgical samples using CE. In the present work effort were made to meet these challenges and to develop a method so that metallurgical samples could be analyzed using CE, which will expand the scope of application of CE.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents :

Hydrochloric acid (37%), AR grade was purchased from Merck, India. Dolomite certified reference material; British Chemical Standards No. 368 was purchased from Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd., UK. Limestone certified reference material; National Metallurgical Laboratory standard No. 71.1 was obtained from CSIR-National Metallurgical Laboratory, Jamshedpur, India. The cationic buffer (pH 3.2), bare fused silica capillary, cation standard containing 100 ppm each of ammonium, potassium, sodium, calcium and magnesium ions and CE grade water was purchased from Agilent Technologies, USA as a part of cation solutions kit (part No. 5064-8206).

Apparatus :

A Capillary Electrophoresis instrument (Make : Agilent Technologies, USA, Model : 7100) equipped with an auto sampler, a UV-Vis diode array detector (DAD), and an inbuilt temperature control system was used in this study. Data was collected using a personal computer in conjunction with ChemStation data acquisition and analysis software. The glassware used was class A glassware purchased from Borosil, India.

Electrophoretic technique :

Electrophoretic separation was carried out using bare fused silica capillary having 50 μm internal diameter, 56 cm effective length (from inlet to detector) and 64.5 cm total length. The new capillary was flushed with cation buffer solution for 15 min at 1 bar pressure. Between analyses the capillary was flushed with cation buffer for 2 min. Since cation buffer is of acidic pH, strongly basic NaOH solution was not used to clean the capillary. The separations were carried out under constant voltage of 30 kV. The analytes were detected in indirect detection mode at 310 nm. Note that at 310 nm the cations have no absorbance whereas the background buffer has strong absorbance; thus making the detection possible in indirect mode. The injection of sample was performed in pressure mode using 50 mbar for 5 s. The separations were carried out at 20 °C. Sample preparation for CE analysis was carried out by dissolving 0.1 g of limestone and dolomite CRM samples (–200 mesh) in 100 ml of 1 N HCl. The solution was filtered through Whatman 40 filter paper and the filtrate was used as the stock solution. 10 ml of the stock solution was then diluted to 100 ml in a volumetric flask and analyzed using CE.

Results and discussion

Analysis of cation standard and preparation of calibration curve :

Before analyzing the dolomite and limestone samples, separation conditions for CE were optimized using synthetic standard solution of cations to get optimized separation of different cations. It was observed that optimum separation of five cations ammonium, potassium, sodium, calcium and magnesium could be obtained using buffer of pH 3.2 at 20 °C and applied voltage of 30 kV. The optimized electropherogram containing 100 ppm each of the above mentioned five cations is shown in Fig. 1. All the peaks are symmetrical and well separated from each other. After optimizing the separation conditions, calibration curve for Ca and Mg analysis was drawn using synthetic standards. One of the major challenges of CE is to analyze concentrated solutions. Dilute solutions (1–30 ppm) can be easily analyzed using CE with good reproducibility¹, but analysis of concentrated solutions often lead to peak broadening and hence poor reproducibility of the result. In the present study, six different standards

Fig. 1. Electropherogram obtained for the standard solution containing 100 ppm of analytes and calibration curves for Ca and Mg.

containing 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 and 100 ppm of the cations were used to draw the calibration curve. The calibration curves for Ca and Mg are shown in Fig. 1. The calibration curves obtained for both Ca and Mg are perfectly linear with very good correlation (0.9999) in the entire calibration range. This indicates that dolomite and limestone solutions containing up to 100 ppm of Ca and Mg can be readily analyzed using CE.

Analysis of dolomite and limestone :

Real samples of limestone and dolomite were then analyzed using the CE instrument. The dolomite and limestone CRMs were used as samples. The electropherograms obtained are shown in Fig. 2. Electropherograms with Ca and Mg ions baseline separated from each other were obtained. The total analysis time was less than 8 min. Two major challenges were faced for successful analysis of dolomite and limestone using CE. The first one is the strong acidic nature of the analysis solution due to acid dissolution of the matrix. This problem was over-

come by choosing an acidic pH buffer (pH 3.2) and increasing the strength of the buffer (30 mM). The second problem encountered was the high concentration of Ca and Mg in the original dissolution solution of the limestone and dolomite samples. The problem was overcome by taking less quantity of sample during sample preparation (0.1 g) and diluting the stock solution to 10 times, which can be done without introducing much dilution error. Diluted solution containing about 100 ppm of Ca and Mg were readily analyzed with good precision and reproducibility.

Repeatability and reproducibility :

Repeatability and reproducibility are two important parameters for any analytical method which need to be verified before the method can be adopted for routine analysis. The repeatability of the CE method for analysis of dolomite was verified by analyzing one dolomite sample solution 10 times under identical CE operating conditions. Similarly, reproducibility of the method was veri-

Fig. 2. Electrophoregrams obtained for analysis of dolomite and limestone.

fied by performing the analysis of dolomite sample by 5 different analysts (starting from sample dissolution to analysis using CE). The data are given in Table 1. The relative standard deviations were low ($< 2\%$) suggesting that the analysis method has good repeatability and reproducibility.

lyzed 5 times following the developed protocol. The analytical values obtained for Ca and Mg along with the uncertainty are presented in Table 2. The certified values with the uncertainties are also given in Table 2 for reference. The obtained values for Ca and Mg are in close

Table 1. Repeatability and reproducibility of data for chemical analysis of dolomite using CE

Parameter		No. of observations										RSD (%)
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Repeatability	Ca (%)	21.8	21.7	22.0	21.8	22.0	21.9	21.8	21.9	21.7	22.0	0.5
	Mg (%)	12.7	12.6	12.7	12.5	12.5	12.6	12.5	12.7	12.6	12.7	0.7
Reproducibility	Ca (%)	21.9	21.5	21.7	22.0	21.8	-	-	-	-	-	0.9
	Mg (%)	12.3	12.7	12.9	12.6	12.5	-	-	-	-	-	1.7

Method validation :

Validation of the developed analytical protocol is critical before its use in day to day analytical practice. Several procedures are available for validating an analytical protocol. Some of them are inter laboratory comparison (ILC), use of Certified Reference Material (CRM) to reproduce the certified values etc. The developed analytical protocol for analysis of limestone and dolomite using CE was validated by analyzing two CRMs, one for dolomite (British Chemical Standard CRM No. 368) and one for limestone (NML CRM No. 71.1). Each sample was ana-

Table 2. Comparison of analytical results obtained for chemical analysis of dolomite and limestone CRMs using CE with the certified values

Sample	Radical	Certified value (%)	Obtained value (%)
Dolomite (BCS CRM 368)	Ca	22.01 ± 0.17	21.92 ± 0.19
	Mg	12.6 ± 0.14	12.79 ± 0.22
Limestone (NML CRM 71.1)	Ca	39.38 ± 0.29	39.05 ± 0.35
	Mg	0.30 ± 0.09	0.37 ± 0.11

agreement with the certified values. Therefore, the developed method is validated and hence can be used in routine analysis.

Comparison of the developed protocol with other analytical methods :

Comparison of the analytical results obtained by different analytical techniques is another way of validating the new developed analytical protocol. In the present study one dolomite CRM sample (British Chemical Standard 368) was analyzed three times each using three different instrumental techniques, i.e. CE, AAS, and ICP-OES. The results obtained are presented in Table 3. The mean value and relative standard deviation (RSD) are given in Table 3 for Ca and Mg content. Data in Table 3 suggest that CE provides better results compared to AAS and ICP-OES techniques for dolomite analysis.

Table 3. Comparison of analytical results obtained for dolomite CRM sample (BCS 368) using different analytical techniques

Technique	Ca (%)			Mg (%)		
	Observations	Mean	RSD (%)	Observations	Mean	RSD (%)
CE	21.95	21.81	1.7	12.76	12.45	3.2
	22.12			11.98		
	21.36			12.61		
AAS	21.32	21.90	2.8	12.31	12.22	5.3
	22.57			12.83		
	21.83			11.52		
ICP-OES	21.71	22.21	1.9	11.76	12.29	4.1
	22.43			12.34		
	22.51			12.79		

Conclusions

A new analytical method was developed for analysis of limestone and dolomite using capillary electrophoresis. The analytical protocol was validated using CRMs. Comparison with other analytical techniques reveal that CE provides better results for Ca and Mg analysis in limestone and dolomite compared to AAS and ICP-OES techniques. The developed protocol is faster, cheaper, and accurate compared to the existing analytical methods and it does not require any gases and avoids all types of interferences.

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